

COMPARATIVE STUDIES OF STATE AND PUBLIC RESPONSES ON MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS AND ROLES OF CIVILIAN JOINT TASK FORCE IN COUNTERTERRORISM OPERATION IN BORNO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study explored public and state responses to the counterterrorism operations of Civilian Joint Task Force in Borno State, Nigeria. The study employed ex-post facto research design and raised two research questions. The sample size consists of 207 public respondents and 196 state respondents, which were selected through proportional sampling technique. Data collection was collected through questionnaires titled ‘Public Response Questionnaire (PRQ) and “State Response Questionnaire” (SRQ). Data collected were analysed using frequency counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The study discovered that the major factors that motivated the rise of CJTF, according to public response were Lack of political will on the part of the government to address the issue of Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 3.64) and the determination of CJTF to protect their communities from Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 3.06). For state response, the main factors identified were lack of political will on the part of the government to address the issue of Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 3.45) and the fact that the CJTF understands the local terrain which enhance their productivity in combating the insurgents (MSV= 3.40). Through public response, the study uncovered that the main roles performed by CJTF were protecting their communities from the attacks of Boko Haram insurgents (MSV= 3.56) and gathering information on Boko Haram for security forces (MSV= 3.02). The state response indicated that CJTF performed the major roles of protecting their communities from the attacks of Boko Haram insurgents (MSV= 3.44) and also assisted in identifying Boko Haram members during search operations (MSV= 3.37).

Keywords: Counterterrorism, Motivational, State, Public, Joint Task Force

INTRODUCTION

Terrorism has become a global phenomenon as no continent is completely free from its devastating outcomes. In Europe, Asia as well as Africa, terrorist activities are pronounced to the extent that these continents have been seriously torched by its attacks. For instance, in Europe, the overall terrorist threat to the security of the EU remains acute, and that the recent attacks in the EU demonstrate the intent and capability of jihadist terrorists to inflict mass casualties on urban populations in an effort to induce a high state of well-publicized terror (The Europol, 2022).

The case of terrorism has had devastating outcomes in the African continent, despite the fact that the modern-day act of terror originated from the advanced nations. Terrorism has contributed in no small measures to the retardation of the progress and development of the African continent. According to Lyman and Morrison (2004), After 9/11, U.S. focus on terrorism in Africa became much more pronounced. For the first time since 1993, the United States deployed a sizeable

contingent of American troops on the continent, with the establishment in late 2002 of the Combined Joint Task Force– Horn of Africa (CJTF-HOA) in Djibouti. In addition, President Bush announced a \$100 million counterterrorism initiative for East Africa and the Horn in 2003.

These ideas clearly showed the degree of vulnerability of the continent of Africa based on the challenges of terrorism. The experiences of terrorism have changed the ways it is prosecuted worldwide, and consequently transforming the identities of terrorists. The manner in which terrorism is spreading, approaches employed by terrorists, the sophisticated technologies used and the resources that goes into planning and executing their operations have absolutely made their operations dynamics and deleterious. The level of casualties and degree of destruction of properties associated with this current wave of terrorism challenged security forces, policymakers and intelligent personnel. Equally, Sierra-Leone and Nigeria shared the same fate with the experiences of non-state volunteer groups fighting for peace in their societies as well as the protection lives and properties. While the event in Sierra-Leone that led to the emergence of the Kamajors was war, the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) that emerged in Nigeria was due to the phenomenon of Boko Haram insurgency. The International Crisis Group (2017) reported that over eleven years (1991-2002) of brutal civil wars in Sierra Leone, killing tens of thousands and displacing up to a quarter of the population, gave birth to one of the most powerful fighting groups known as the Kamajors. The document further revealed that this group evolved from bands of young men defending their villages and that its trajectory over the course of the long war demonstrates how vigilante groups can be effective in community protectors and, at times, military auxiliaries, principally by virtue of their superior local knowledge (p.3). On the other hand, CJTF emerged as a result of the continuous attacks of Boko Haram insurgents and the inability of the security forces to contain its excesses in the northeast, Nigeria. Ripples Nigeria (2020) indicated that the creation of civilian JTF as part of the mechanism for combating the menaces of Boko Haram terrorism in Nigeria represents a veritable example of citizen-driven communal response to security challenges and an indication of how terrorism can be tackled and prevented. Thus, these self-defense groups in communities were occasioned by common occurrences of the continuous state of insecurity and the failure of security forces to protect lives and properties. In the case of CJTF, Bamidele (2020) asserted that the CJTF came as a ‘child of necessity,’ as compelled by the menace of Boko Haram, given its attacks on innocent citizens in Borno State, and the incapacity of the Nigerian military forces in the early days of insurgency. This statement can be seen as a general issue that run through societies where a pathway was created for the emergence of security provisioning outfits in communities in counterterrorism theatres in Africa.

However, as the counterterrorism operations progresses, public and state perceptions concerning the activities of CJTF were acknowledged with mixed feelings, in which some people reported that they have deviated from their “good works” to engaging in different negative behaviours that painted them as human rights violators, extorters and victimizers. Kwaja (2018) reported that while the use of civilian vigilantes has won praise for helping to drive away many Boko Haram members, residents complained that the same CJTF harassed, insulted and manhandled motorists at checkpoints. Also, CJTF has been fingered in several occasions as committing acts of hooliganism, robbery, vandalism, rape and thuggery (Maiangwa, 2017).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Community-based security related vigilantes (CBSV) are not a new creation, however, in this contemporary time characterised by high incidents of terrorist invasions as well as counterterrorism operations, their relevance and legitimacy

have soar tremendously in societies experiencing a great deal of insecurity. Their acceptability is practically based on their potential to provide security and safety in communities, which have created the opportunity for local people to go about their normal businesses peacefully. Onuoha (2009) rightly noted that while these groups (i.e non-state security forces) may differ in their motivations, form, size, organisations, and functions, they share one thing in common; the capacity to perpetuate organised violence whether in opposition or in support of the state. Thus, there are evidences to the fact that non-state volunteer groups may suddenly become bad to the people they are meant to defend and protect. Okolo (2021) observed that there are indications in which members of the non-state volunteer groups have been accused of illegal torture, detention of innocent persons and violation of the rights of people, while carrying out their duties, which have been giving members of the public serious concern about what they may become in the future if they are not checked. Apart from this, there are also situations in which members of the non-state volunteer groups used their position to pursue personal vendetta against people they had rift with before joining the group (Okolo, 2021)

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This study will be beneficial to the various levels of government, policy makers, Civilian Joint Task Force and other community-based security related vigilantes, researchers and the general public. This research work will enable the various levels of government involved in sponsoring or supporting Civilian Joint Task Force to understand their operational dynamics and patterns. The Specific Objective are to:

- (i) Ascertain the Motivation for the involvement of CJTF in Counterterrorism Operations
- (ii) Ascertain the Functional roles carried out by CJTF in communities to prevent Boko Haram attacks

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the Motivation for the involvement of CJTF in Counterterrorism Operations?
2. What are the Functional roles carried out by CJTF in communities to prevent Boko Haram attacks?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

This study is underscored by Social Exchange Theory. The theory was propounded by the sociologist George Homans (1950). Homans was looking at how human actions and interactions were influenced by mutual rewards. People will accept something or do something or agree with something because of the benefit it has for them. Inversely, people will reject something or refuse to do something if they see no reward in it for them.

Behaviour that is rewarded in general continues (up to the limit of diminishing marginal utility). His first proposition, the success proposition, states that behaviour that generates positive consequences is likely to be repeated. The second proposition, the stimulus proposition, states that behaviour that has been rewarded on such occasions in the past will be performed in similar situations. The value proposition, the third proposition, specifies that the more valuable the result of an action is to an actor, the more likely that action is to be performed. The fourth proposition, the deprivation-satiation proposition, qualifies the stimulus proposition introducing the general ideal of diminishing marginal utility: the more often a person has recently received a particular reward for an action, the less valuable is an additional unit of that reward. Finally, the fifth proposition specifies when individuals will react emotionally to different reward situations. People will become angry and aggressive when they do not receive what they anticipate. Based on this social interaction that is not rewarding and

is not cost-effective will eventually cease, or at least lose the support of the party losing from the interaction. Except such a relationship is forced to continue, it will eventually die off. It is important to note that social exchange as Homans put it is both tangible and intangible. He argued that “Social behaviour is an exchange of goods, material goods but also non-material ones, such as the symbols of approval or prestige (Homans, 1958).”

Conceptual framework

Terrorism is a broad concept that has been described by different scholars at different point in time. Freedman (2002) is of the view that terrorism has historically been seen as a strategic occurrence, which fluctuates according to religion, geographical location and culture. Therefore, it cannot be rigidly defined. It has been used as an instrument by revolutionaries and nationalists and even by governments to maintain state control. Defining and understanding terrorism depends greatly on the perspective of the beholder because one man’s terrorist could be seen as another man’s freedom fighter. That is, a terrorist act, past or present could be seen by someone as an act of revolution and ideological freedom, it could be seen by another as a cruel senseless act of ideological violence. In the submission of FBI (2006), they described terrorism as violent acts that appear to be intended to intimidate or coerce a civilian population; influence the policy of a government by intimidation or coercion; or affect the conduct of a government by mass destruction, assassination or kidnapping and occur primarily outside the territorial jurisdiction of the United States or transcend national boundaries in terms of the means by which they are accomplished, the persons they appear intended to intimidate or coerce, or the locale in which their perpetrators operate or seek asylum. From the description of FBI, some points are worthy of expatiation.

There are many terrorism groups in the world who threat world some are Islamic state, Hamas, Hezbollah, Boko Haram, Taliban, Al-Qaeda and many more. Terrorism can be categorized according to the motivation of the terrorist groups into three different categories: nationalist, political and religious. Nationalist terrorism includes terrorist actions that are generated from the separatist movements, independence fighters and resistance movements of a certain region (Krishna, 2015). All the terrorist movements can be seen as political, so in this context, political terrorism refers to the extreme right- or left-wing political movements. Also, terrorist actions designed by one cause movements such as animal rights’ movements and anti-nuclear movements can be labelled under political terrorism. Religious terrorism has its roots in the religious ideology or cult movements such as millennialism or judgment day movements. Nowadays, religious terrorism is easily connected only with Islam, but includes other religions as well (Kullberg, 2011). Ariel (2007) described terrorism as the substrate, application of violence or threatened violence intended to show panic in the society, to weaken or even overthrow the incumbent and bring about political change. Karacasulu (2005) avers that terrorism is the act of violence committed against innocent persons or non-combatant that are intended to achieve political ends through fear and intimidations. Overtly, terrorism has more frequently been associated with a crime committed against the poor and the underprivileged by disenfranchising them. Thus, by design, terrorism is an unpredictable use of violence against individuals, groups, community or nation to attain the goal of the perpetrators. This may include, but not limited to the overthrowing, destabilizing or replacing the existing system and institution or a retaliation for the hurt and harm committed (Wilson, 2010). Notably, there are several motivations that strut terrorist attacks on the unsuspecting victims. These motivations include, but not limited to, political, social, moral, personal and religious. According to Ali (1997), he noted that terrorism has been used all through history throughout the world by states, organizations, groups and individuals. Ngige, Badekale and HammanJoda (2016) described terrorism as practiced and justified by terrorist themselves, is a tool used to achieve a specific outcome by using force or violence on one segment of society with the primary goal of causing fear in the larger society to make changes in that society. However, based on the

work of Biernatzki (2002), the United Nations General Assembly offered one definition of terrorism that has apparently been deemed serviceable for most purposes: criminal acts intended or calculated to provoke a state of terror in the general public, a group of persons or particular persons for political purposes, whatever the considerations of a political, philosophical, ideological, racial, ethnic, religious or other nature that may be invoked to justify them. It is an unlawful use of force or violence against persons or property to intimidate or coerce a government, the civilian population, or any segment thereof, in furtherance of political or social objectives.

Review of related empirical studies

Yusuf (2014) in his study titled: The Role of Civilian JTF in Tackling Boko Haram Problems in Borno. The study dwells on how the Civilian JTF helped in countering Boko Haram insurgents. The objectives of the study were to identify the purposes of the Civilian JTF, to determine the socio-economic characteristics of the Civilian JTF, to find out the factors that led to their rise and identify the challenges they face. The study was a survey that used a questionnaire to obtain information from members of the Civilian JTF in two local government areas; Maiduguri and Jere local government areas respectively. The study finds out that most members of the Civilian JTF were youths. Most of the youths joined Civilian JTF, to take revenge for their loved ones killed by members of the Boko Haram insurgency; revenge and defence became the driving force behind Civilian JTF. The study also pointed out that some members of the Civilian JTF had risen to fight back when their communities and their lives became unsafe. They fought back to protect themselves and their communities. The study also revealed that the failure of the Military JTF to identify and differentiate between innocent youths and Boko Haram members was one of the major reasons why the Civilian JTF came up to assist the Military JTF in identifying and capturing the Boko Haram insurgency members. Like most other studies, this study did not focus on the cultural dimension of the Boko Haram insurgency. It also lacked wider coverage of affected areas of Borno State. It focused only on the activities of the Civilian JTF, without looking at the activities of Boko Haram, which is the precursor of the Civilian JTF. Raphael and James (2016) in their work examine the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) on the War against Boko Haram in North East of Nigeria. The focal point of the study is on the utilization of non-governmental security agencies in countering Boko Haram in northeast. The study highlighted the pros and cons of the engagement of the non-conventional security outfit in countering Boko Haram. The study also examined the role played by the Civilian Joint Task Force (JTF) side by side the Nigerian Military and their distinguished impact on the countering Boko Haram. The study made use of secondary data and adopted failed state theory to explain its phenomenon. The study concluded that the nature of counter insurgency operation against Boko Haram, the terrain they choose to occupy and fight in, their style of offensive and war, left the military with little choice but to collaborate with civilians, if they must make headway. Though ill-equipped and untrained in the art of warfare, the Civilian JTF has remained immensely helpful with their familiar knowledge of geography and difficult terrain in the North East as well as capable of identifying the real Boko Haram terrorists. They discovered that the combined effort of the Military and the Civilian JTF has resulted in the current success recorded in the war against the insurgency culminating in the taking back of local governments and major towns hitherto at the hands of the terrorists.

Gap the study intends to fill

It is clear from the literature reviewed that Civilian Joint Task Force gathered momentum in terms of research outcomes. However, many of the researches were based on functional roles of the group as well as what they able to be accomplished since they were established. Some studies discussed their welfare and state of logistics for positive outcomes

in their operations. Some other studies equally looked at how their operations were perceived by communities due to their counterterrorism activities.

METHODOLOGY

Area of the study

Borno State was created in 1976 out of the then North-Eastern State and occupies a land mass of 70,898km². The state is located within latitude 10 N and 14 N and longitude 11 30 E and 14 45 E and has a population of 6,111,500 million people (City Population Projection, 2022). The state has twenty-seven (27) Local Government Areas, grouped into three Senatorial Districts, namely: Borno Central, Borno North and Borno South Senatorial Districts. The local government areas are grouped under these various senatorial districts.

Research design

This study adopted ex-post facto research design. According to Tuckman (1972), ex-post facto research design is a study in which the researcher examines the effects of a naturalistically.

Population of study

The population of the study was nine hundred and ninety-one thousand and nine hundred (991,900).

Sample and sampling technique,

The sample for the study was drawn from the public, which are community members affected by Boko Haram insurgency, in which security forces in conjunction with CJTF fought them. For the public, three local government areas considered hard hit by the insurgents and that witnessed the intervention of the security forces with the CJTF were selected from the three senatorial districts in the state. Thus, one local government area was selected from each of the district. Also, the security forces that engaged in counterterrorism operations alongside with the CJTF, and that are knowledgeable on the activities of the CJTF were used as samples in the study. Therefore, 202, proportional representation was used to determine each of the samples that were collected in each of the local government areas out of 30,000 CJTF.

Instrument for data collection

The instruments that were used for data collection for the study were through structured questionnaires, made up of the state response and public response. The questionnaires were titled Public Responses Questionnaire (PRQ) and State Responses Questionnaire (SRQ). The item statements reflected 4-point Likert-scale rating with the following responses: Strongly Agree (SA); Agree (A); Strongly Disagree (SD) and Disagree(D).

Validation of instrument,

The instruments for the study were validated using face and content validity. Copies of the instruments were submitted to three experts in the field of Peace and Security Studies for validation.

Reliability of instrument

The reliability of the instruments was ascertained through a pilot test. This was done by administering copies of the questionnaire to 20 respondents in communities affected by insurgency in Adamawa State. Specifically, Gombi local government area was used because the locality experienced Boko Haram invasion and interventions from security forces and CJTF. The data collected were subjected to a Cronbach alpha statistical analysis to ascertain the internal consistency of the items on the questionnaire. The results from the reliability tests indicated that the instruments were adjudged as reliable. This

is because the high degree of the Cronbach alpha coefficient. The instrument for state had a coefficient of 0.7 and that of the public had 0.75, which were considered as high and acceptable. Thus, the instruments were considered as reliable.

Method of data analysis

The data collected were analysed with frequency counts, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and t-test. The personal characteristics of the respondents were analysed using mean, standard deviation and percentage. Also, the research questions that guided the study were answered with frequency counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation. For the purpose of decision-making with respect to the data analysed, a cut-off point of 4 point Likert rating scale was used. Consequently, any item in which its Mean Square Value (MSV) is lower than 2.5 was adjudged as a weak factor or disagree. While the items with a mean score equal to 2.5 or greater than 2.5 were considered as a strong factor or agree.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the Motivation for the involvement of CJTF in Counterterrorism Operations?

Table 1: Motivation for the involvement CJTF in Counterterrorism Operations

S/N	Items	STATE RESPONSE					PUBLIC RESPONSE				
		SA	A	D	SD	MSV	SA	A	D	SD	MSV
1.	Lack of political will on the part of the government to decisively address the issue of Boko Haram insurgency give rise to the emergence of civilian joint task force	110	70	10	6	3.45	140	60	5	3	3.64
2.	The activities of security operatives seem to be unproductive in combating the menaces of Boko Haram insurgent which make civilian joint task force to arise	81	68	30	17	3.07	63	104	7	33	2.95
3.	Civilian joint task force understands the local terrain which enhance their productivity in combating the insurgents.	90	98	5	3	3.4	78	72	28	29	2.96
4.	The determination of the civilian joint task force to protect their communities inspired their participation in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency	85	94	10	9	3.32	82	71	39	15	3.06
5.	Civilian joint task force believes that they are equal to the task hence, they get involved in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency	82	72	20	20	3.08	85	65	34	23	3.02
6.	Lack of trust on the part of security agencies in fighting Boko Haram led to the involvement of	76	59	22	39	2.88	60	89	15	45	2.81

	civilian joint task force in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency										
7.	Civilian joint task force joined the fight in order to augment the shortage of the security forces for effective operations	65	90	23	18	3.03	79	70	29	29	2.96

Table 1 showed the factors that motivated the involvement of CJTF in counterterrorism operations in Borno State. The respondents for the state agreed that all the item were factors that prompted the engagement of CJTF in counterterrorism operations. However, the major factors responsible for involvement of CJTF in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency were lack of political will on the part of the government to decisively address the issue of Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 3.45); Civilian joint task force understands the local terrain which enhance their productivity in combating the insurgents(MSV= 3.40); and the determination of the civilian joint task force to protect their communities inspired their participation in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 3.32). Some other factors identified by respondents for the state, that equally encouraged CJTF to participate in counterterrorism operations were Civilian joint task force believes that they are equal to the task hence, they get involved in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 3.08); the activities of security operatives seem to be unproductive in combating the menaces of Boko Haram insurgent which make civilian joint task force to arise (MSV= 3.07); Civilian joint task force joined the fight in order to augment the shortage of the security forces for effective operations (MSV= 3.03) and lack of trust on the part of security agencies in fighting Boko Haram led to the involvement of civilian joint task force in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 2.88).

On the part of the respondents for the public, the major factors indicated by them as motivating the involvement of CJTF in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency were lack of political will on the part of the government to decisively address the issue of Boko Haram insurgency give rise to the emergence of civilian joint task force (MSV= 3.64); the determination of the civilian joint task force to protect their communities inspired their participation in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 3.06) and Civilian joint task force believes that they are equal to the task hence, they get involved in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency (MSV= 3.02). The respondents for the public equally identified the fact that Civilian joint task force joined the fight in order to augment the shortage of the security forces for effective operations (MSV= 2.96); Civilian joint task force understands the local terrain which enhance their productivity in combating the insurgents (MSV= 2.96); the activities of security operatives seem to be unproductive in combating the menaces of Boko Haram insurgent which make civilian joint task force to arise (MSV= 2.95) and lack of trust on the part of security agencies in fighting Boko Haram led to the involvement of civilian joint task force in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency(MSV= 2.81). It is clear from the analysis that there was agreement between the two groups on most of the statements, however, the respondents expressed strong views with regards to the fact that the government lack the political will to ensure that the issue of Boko Haram insurgency is decisively tackled. Also the civilian joint task force was determined to protect their communities based on the dimensions of suffering that their people are passing through in the hands of Boko Haram insurgents.

Research Question 2: What are the Functional roles carried out by CJTF in communities to prevent Boko Haram attacks?

Table 2: Functional roles carried out by CJTF in communities to prevent Boko Haram attacks

S/N	Items	STATE RESPONSE					PUBLIC RESPONSE				
		SA	A	D	SD	MSV	SA	A	D	SD	MSV
1.	Protecting their communities from the continuous attacks of Boko Haram insurgents.	95	96	2	3	3.44	126	72	8	1	3.56
2.	Gathering of information (intelligence) on the activities of Boko Haram for security forces	84	90	7	15	3.24	70	96	17	24	3.02
3.	Civilian joint task force assisted in identifying Boko Haram members during search operations	95	88	4	9	3.37	78	81	19	29	3
4.	Civilian joint task force arrested suspected insurgents/criminals in the community.	90	88	7	11	3.31	70	80	32	25	2.94
5.	Guiding the security forces on how to navigate the unfamiliar terrain or local communities to provide security	84	78	16	18	3.16	84	68	26	29	3
6.	Sensitization of communities on how /when to act to safeguard themselves from Boko Haram	70	74	19	33	2.92	75	70	22	40	2.87
7.	Civilian joint task force enhanced community trust in the course of the fight against Boko Haram insurgents	73	78	25	20	3.04	60	80	31	36	2.79

Table 2 reflected the functional roles carried out by CJTF in communities to prevent the attacks of Boko Haram insurgents. The respondents for the state and public agreed to the statements raised with respect to the roles played by CJTF in communities in Borno State. The respondents for the state indicated that CJTF performed the following roles: protecting their communities from the continuous attacks of Boko Haram insurgents (MSV= 3.44); civilian joint task force assisted in identifying Boko Haram members during search/ operations (MSV= 3.37); civilian joint task force arrested suspected insurgents/criminals in the community (MSV= 3.31); gathering of information (intelligence) on the activities of Boko Haram for security forces (MSV= 3.24) and guiding the security forces on how to navigate the unfamiliar terrain or local communities to provide security (MSV= 3.16). These functional roles were considered as the main tasks carried out by CJTF to restore peace and stability in their communities. The respondents for the public pointed out that CJTF executing the following responsibilities in their communities: protecting their communities from the continuous attacks of Boko Haram insurgents (MSV= 3.56); gathering of information (intelligence) on the activities of Boko Haram for security forces (MSV= 3.02); guiding the security forces on how to navigate the unfamiliar terrain or local communities to provide security (MSV= 3.00) and civilian joint task force assisted in identifying Boko Haram members during search operations (MSV= 3.00). Apart from these responsibilities, some other tasks conducted by CJTF in communities to restore peace and stability were arresting suspected insurgents/criminals in the community (MSV= 2.94); sensitization of communities on how /when to act to safeguard

themselves from Boko Haram (MSV= 2.87) and enhancing community trust in the course of the fight against Boko Haram insurgents (MSV= 2.79). The two groups agreed majorly that CJTF protected their communities from the attacks of Boko Haram insurgents and they assisted in identifying Boko Haram members during search operations in communities in Borno State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Factors that motivated the involvement of Civilian Joint Task Force in Counterterrorism Operations

The study discovered that CJTF were motivated to engage in counterterrorism operations due to lack of political will on the part of the government to decisively address the issue of Boko Haram insurgency; the determination of the civilian joint task force to protect their communities; civilian joint task force believes that they are equal to the task hence, they get involved in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency; Civilian joint task force joined the fight in order to augment the shortage of the security forces for effective operations and the activities of security operatives seem to be unproductive in combating the menaces of Boko Haram insurgent which make civilian joint task force to arise. The position of Shire (2021) captured the essence of involvement of community task force. The writer indicated that local communities sponsor self-defense militias to fill the political, social, and/or security gaps that emerge in the context of a state's inability or unwillingness to safeguard communities' interests against insurgent attacks.

Also, Salihu (2021) pointed out that the decision to deploy indiscriminate military force against Boko Haram has failed to diminish the capacity of the insurgency; rather its counter productiveness has alienated the region's civilian population, fostering widespread dissatisfaction amongst the affected population. These assertions are in accord with the results of this study. Ozden and Kwabe (2019) posited that the CJTF which is made of indigenous people of Borno State have been able to lead attacks jointly with the state institution and their skills have been required in mapping out attacks against Boko Haram. Al Chukwuma (2017) observed that the rise of anti-Boko Haram vigilantes such as CJTF in North-East Nigeria was necessitated by the need for the civilians to protect themselves amidst the apparent inability or failure of the government forces to guarantee their security. The need to protect communities and failure of government forces motivated the emergence of CJTF in the Borno State. According to Bamidele (2020), the determination to fight back, and the frustration with the military forces' lack of capacity to prevent the incessant attacks, led to the setting up of what is now known as the 'CJTF'. These statements are in accord with the findings of this study. It was discovered in this study that civilian joint task force joined the fight in order to augment the shortage of the security forces for effective operations and the activities of security operatives seem to be unproductive in combating the menaces of Boko Haram insurgent which make civilian joint task force to arise. These findings are in tandem with the report of Watch List (2014) that "self-defense forces have become widespread in North East Nigeria as civilians have taken up arms against JAS (Boko Haram) to defend their communities, filling a security void left by the government security forces. CJTF emergence is not only based in places where the government lacks capacity to protect local people from Boko Haram terrorism, but also where the government is believed to be untrustworthy (Nigerian Watch, 2014). This idea indicated that CJTF come up because of the activities of security operatives seem to be unproductive in combating the menaces of Boko Haram insurgents. The findings of this study are in line with these statements and assertions. Premium Times (2013) reported that civilian JTF arises from the perception that the government is doing nothing to guarantee the safety of north-east region. Thus, CJTF emerged because of their determination to protect their communities because of the inability of the government forces to prevent the attack of Boko Haram insurgency. Also, Bamidele (2020) indicated that CJTF is just a group of volunteers who took their sticks according to native language Kanuri (gora) in which

they use in fighting the BH. The author stated further that what compel them to kick against the activities of BH, due to frustration and frequent attacks on people. Inspired by the zeal of CJTF, government now recognize their efforts and gave them support. These ideas are in tandem with the findings of this study.

Functional roles conducted by Civilian Joint Task Force in communities to prevent the attacks of Boko Haram insurgents

The study also uncovered that functional roles carried out by CJTF in communities to prevent Boko Haram attacks were protecting their communities from the continuous attacks of Boko Haram insurgents; gathering of information (intelligence) on the activities of Boko Haram for security forces; guiding the security forces on how to navigate the unfamiliar terrain or local communities to provide security; civilian joint task force assisted in identifying Boko Haram members during search operations and civilian joint task force arrested suspected insurgents/criminals in the community. Owonikoko and Onuoha (2019) posited that CJTF have been able to identify and arrest suspected members of the Boko Haram given their robust knowledge and familiarity of the terrain and people. This is because they were familiar with the environment, their communities and the people. According to Amaike (2017) civilian joint task force has been helpful in providing useful information (intelligence) that has boosted the counterterrorism operations in Nigeria. Also, Nagarajan (2019) reported that Civilians credit the CJTF for bringing some stability and safety to Borno state. They believe members of the group are proactive in investigating reports received from community members, sharing information with civilians, and serving as a bridge between communities and security forces which enables the transfer of information and intelligence. According to Agbiboa (2015). CJTF helped in the improvement of civil-military relations. In fact, in some areas the yan gora right alongside Nigerian soldiers and provide the military with local intelligence and manpower. Thus, CJTF performed critical security in communities in Borno State. These ideas are in agreement with the findings of this study. Owonikoko and Onuoha (2019) asserted that the CJTF in Borno State has helped to curtail military attacks on innocent civilians and also assisted in decimating Boko Haram. Al Chukwuma (2017) revealed that apart from CJTF policing their local communities, these volunteer vigilantes have been assisting the military in identifying, arresting and spying suspected insurgents and they have largely facilitated the major breakthroughs made by the military in terms of high-profile arrests of suspected insurgents as well as rescue of their hostages.

CJTF functions in such a manner that they arrested a considerable number of insurgents in the course of operations. Equally, Jentsch *et al* (2015) Indicated that the overstretched Nigerian military was quick to spot the importance of the CJTF as both a “force multiplier” and “a feasible and effective means of counterinsurgency, providing valuable local knowledge and efficient means to collect intelligence. In the vein, Agbiboa (2020) pointed out that the CJTF’s efficiency in identifying and arresting Boko Haram members, aided by its local knowledge and social networks, forced Boko Haram to decamp from Maiduguri to remote parts of Borno state (the Gwoza hills and the Mandara mountains). These ideas are in agreement with the findings of this study. Also, Agbiboa (2015) observed Civilian Joint Task Force are used to track down Boko Haram members in their communities and turn them in to state security forces or kill themselves. The feat they were able to accomplish were as a result of their numerical advantage and local knowledge. These factors enable them to drive Boko Haram out of the city by identifying their member’s house by house (Agbiboa, 2015). These ideas are in tandem with the findings of this study.

CONCLUSION

The state and public operators both agreed that Lack of political will on the part of the government to decisively address the issue of Boko Haram insurgency give rise to the emergence of civilian joint task force and a major motivational hindrance to control Boko Haram in Borno State. The functional role that cut-across the state and public counterterrorism operators is that they are protecting their communities from the continuous attacks of Boko Haram insurgents

RECOMMENDATION

The collaborative mechanism of Civilian Joint Task Force with state security force should be strengthened and fortified by the government in order to encourage more performance in terms of provision of security and fighting of crimes in communities. Apart from this, the collaborative attitudes of the groups will enhance their productivity in such a manner that Boko Haram insurgents will be handled decisively and their attacks forestalled for peace to reign in communities in the state.

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